

Development of social notes sharing system under the new normal educational approach

Jhon Marco R. Ramirez*, Ian Jasper A. Paypon, Katrina Janelle G. Barretto, Jannel C. Berrey, Alvin Jason A. Virata
Information Technology Department, School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoar City, Cavite, Philippines
*Corresponding author

Abstract

One of the industries most affected by technological advancement is education. The main objective of this study is to develop a social note-sharing system that addresses the issues in emerging technologies with the new normal educational approaches. The research focuses on the development of a system that will help students resolve issues addressed as portability, reliability, and efficiency of information and data sharing among peers up to different students with different schools sharing information for the public and private information. The design of the system has an entity-relationship model that will allow every user to access the system everywhere, anywhere, and at any time of the day.

Keywords: *Note-sharing; New normal education; Learning Management System (LMS); Web-based system.*

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Introduction

Teachers, students, and even parents find learning in the new normal education to be difficult. In blended learning, all assignments are turned in and graded online using technology, combining online and offline learning approaches (Paramount Direct, 2020). Most students in the Philippines are currently experiencing difficulties with online classes, and some of them are having a hard time communicating or interacting with other students or their professors; some are hard to reach out to, while some are having a limited workforce and technological capabilities (Arado, 2020). With technology in education, users can construct new learning platforms, explore new opportunities, emulate real-life scenarios, and view everyday objects from completely different perspectives. Even more successful than standardized learning, it enables the learners to have a personalized educational experience (Heard, 2020).

In the new normal of education, all schools will have mixed or online courses (Ancheta & Ancheta, 2020; Tanhueco-Tumapon, 2020). With regards to the new normal education, this implies more exertion from students and more tolerance from professors, and the other way around. Students need to pay attention to their educators, yet instructors who are responsive and understanding should also pay attention to the concerns of students (Mayzenberg, 2020; Pacheco, 2021). Social interaction would facilitate the exchange of knowledge and experience, leading to remarkable results (Heard, 2020).

Social notes must be arranged more closely than personal letters so that they could have a particular function (Hollowell, 2020). In any event, as students dig deeper into details, turning the main ideas and broad concepts into facts and specific details, they gain a great deal more information and comprehension (Zetlin, 2019). Providing social and emotional support to students during distant learning can help to make routines less unpleasant and keep the student's control and focus (Morin, 2020). Maintaining best practices can be one of the strategies in facing the new normal of education; regardless of asynchronous or synchronous classes choosing to utilize methods and strategies for running a class, they must keep best

practices for guidance. Setting an effort to discover the nuances of students with regards to the digital involvement would allow educators to more precisely cater to their students' necessities (Bustamante & Almarode, 2020).

The development of this study will play an important role in conveying new normal educational approaches. The main objective of this study is to develop a social note-sharing system that addresses the issues in emerging technologies in the new normal educational approaches and intends to give an efficient tool for sharing and exchanging a variety of lecture notes and resources to the students and teachers. Specifically, the study aims to first analyze the problem of the current situation regarding lack of learning materials and resources and facilitate sharing of course material and interactive engaging tools in which the researchers would establish an online learning tool that would interchange ideas using note sharing to support and help improve the learning process in education. Second is to apply Dashboard and Events feature in a user-friendly web-based social note-sharing system that allows users to identify and organize their notes, which would increase student learning experience and improve teacher teaching approaches. The last is to conduct code reviews to manage defects in code development, which includes prioritizing those defects that will validate the search technology method applied in the system.

This system would mainly focus on helping students who are currently experiencing difficulties exploring resources. Students can learn from personal notes that were shared by the teachers and their fellow students using the social note-sharing system. This study is limited to covering topics related to the social note-sharing system. It was also limited to the teachers and students at St. Dominic College of Asia, as the system lacks editing layout capabilities and is incapable of providing tutorials, online courses, and programs.

Methodology

This study is a self-contained research study that evaluates the ability of applying knowledge to conduct solutions to practical problems. To achieve the objectives, researchers utilized the Agile System Development Life Cycle technique, in which it comprises steps that are required for building, maintaining, changing, replacing, or enhancing the components of system software. It consists of six steps that include the following: Requirements, Design, Development, Testing, Deployment, and Review. The potential subjects that were considered relevant in this study are the targeted end users and expert users. The respondents consist of 80 students from end users and 20 expert users who came from an IT field. The research instrument is survey questionnaires, which are made from Google Forms, and the software evaluation is based on the ISO 9126 software quality standards, which have six categories that include the following: Functionality, Reliability, Usability, Efficiency, Maintainability, and Portability of the development of web-based systems in the new normal educational approach.

This system was developed using the laptop with specifications of a dual-core CPU, Windows 7, 4 GB of RAM, and 100 mbps of Wi-Fi connection. The software programs used are Visual Studio 2019, Internet Information Services, and Microsoft SQL Server. The design of this system is simple and user-friendly, as it would let the user navigate the features since it can be quickly understood. The development of the system would not be done using software programs, which are Visual Studio 2019, Internet Information Services, and Microsoft SQL Server. The researchers deployed the system on Ovhcloud server, which is in Singapore. For the domain name, the researchers bought it on Namecheap. The system was later reviewed to determine if it was feasible.

The researchers let the users, first-year students from the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology at St. Dominic College of Asia, test the system for one week (October 13-20) before having the software evaluation. According to Cronbach's alpha rules, which validate the reliability of the gathered data, the value of computed Cronbach's alpha is 0.92, which is interpreted as excellent.

A system flowchart, which shows the decisions taken at different levels and the path that data follows in a system, has been developed by the researchers. It displays the flow of the Social Notes Sharing System.

Figure 1. System Flow Chart

To determine the relationship of data in this system, the researchers created the Entity Relationship Diagram. Based on Figure 2, the User Profile relates to the Note, Notes Users, and Activity, while on the other hand, the Note is associated with the Notes User, Notes View, and the Attachment.

Figure 2. Entity Relationship Diagram

The System Framework is the ASP.NET Model-View-Controller, which is used to design patterns that help in achieving the separation of concerns (Figure 3). When the user interacts with the view, the view notifies the controller, updates the model, notifies the view of any changes, and then updates the view by grabbing model data. Requests are routed using the MVC pattern to a Controller, who oversees interacting with the Model to carry out operations or obtain data. The Controller then selects the View to show and gives it the Model. Based on the information gathered in the Model, the View creates the final page.

Figure 3. System Framework

The researchers gathered data on their respondents, which is divided into expert and end users, using a survey, which they used to utilize a five-point Likert scale to measure how satisfied users were with the system’s functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability that was based on the software evaluation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the scale, range, and interpretation of the five-point Likert scale, which indicates whether the system’s level of agreement is Strongly Agree, Agree, Neither, Disagree, or Strongly Disagree. The overall rating of development of the web-based social note sharing system in the new normal educational approach is expected to be at 2.51 or higher; this variable would consider that the project is feasible, and this would illustrate if the users were satisfied with the development of this project.

Table 1. Level of Satisfaction

Scale	Range of Menu Value	Qualitative Information
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree
3	2.51 – 3.50	Neither
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree

The level of satisfaction and respondent frequency are used to display the overall response of the expert-user and end-user. The level of satisfaction experienced by both expert users and end users is **Agree**, with a mean score of 4.46.

Table 2. Overall Level of Satisfaction Based on Respondent's Distribution

Category	Expert User	End User	Overall Level of Satisfaction	Rating
Functionality	4.46	4.49	4.48	Agree
Reliability	4.45	4.34	4.40	Agree
Usability	4.48	4.46	4.47	Agree
Efficiency	4.52	4.46	4.49	Agree
Maintainability	4.51	4.38	4.44	Agree
Portability	4.47	4.48	4.47	Agree
Average	4.48	4.43	4.46	Agree

Upon the completion of the study, the researchers assess and analyze the important categories that are crucial to the project. These classifications pertain to the system's functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability when the expected objectives are achieved. Below is a summary of the results showing the highest mean for both end and expert users with the overall satisfaction.

Functionality. The total average for the End User is 4.5 and for the Expert User is 4.5 which is both Agree in the level of satisfaction. Hence, the overall satisfaction of the system's functionality is 4.5, indicating that the system makes the best use of its inputs measured as the user's utilization of assets in connection to the completeness and accuracy of objectives accomplished satisfying the user's desired functionalities.

Reliability. The total average for the End User is 4.3 and for the Expert User is 4.5 which is both Agree in the level of satisfaction. Hence, the overall satisfaction of the system's reliability is 4.4 indicating that the system's performance is good when used under specified conditions. The system proves its reliability by functioning well even though they may have interruptions that occur. The system fulfills its duty and all the functions that are included there are operating and functioning well.

Usability. The total average for the End User is 4.5 and for the Expert User is 4.5 which is both Agree in the level of satisfaction. Hence, the overall satisfaction of the system's usability is 4.5 indicating that the systems can be understood, learned, and used. The system's performance proves its quality by allowing users to achieve their goals in an efficient manner that would benefit and satisfy its users.

Efficiency. The total average for the End User is 4.5 and for the Expert User is 4.5 which indicates Agree and Strongly Agree in the level of satisfaction. Hence, the overall satisfaction of the system's efficiency is 4.5 indicating that the system provides performance in accordance with the resources used. The system is proved to be efficient for the users because of its simple design and functions. It makes the users easier to figure out what functions and keys are used for.

Maintainability. The total average for the End User is 4.4 and for the Expert User is 4.5 which indicates Agree and Strongly Agree in the level of satisfaction. Hence, the overall satisfaction of the system's maintainability is 4.4 indicating that the system is maintained. The system is well organized by having a model-view controller to track redundancy so that it can be repaired or fixed while it is being used by the users.

Portability. The total average for the End User is 4.5 and for the Expert User is 4.5 which is both Agree in the level of satisfaction. Hence, the overall satisfaction of the system's portability is 4.5, indicating that the software can be ported from one environment to another. Since it is web-based, the work necessary to adapt computer software to another could be very simple.

In general, the system was evaluated by 80 End Users and 20 Expert Users, with the highest in terms of **Efficiency** and lowest in terms of **Reliability**. With the average of 4.5 for Expert Users and 4.4 for End Users, the overall level satisfaction is 4.5, which was interpreted as **Agree**.

Therefore, this platform proves itself to be a very user-friendly site where the student and teacher meet their expectations about sharing notes. This result agrees with Porcel et al. (2018), which revealed a high system performance in terms of precision, as well as great satisfaction and usability for some people. Social network solutions assist students and institutions in gaining access to online materials provided through social networks to improve learning techniques. The lecture notes provide vital context and material. It is an excellent method for assisting students in identifying key themes in a lesson.

Conclusion

In the final analysis, the researchers prove it by first analyzing the lack of learning materials and resources and facilitating the sharing of course materials and interactive, engaging tools. The researchers conclude that establishing a social notes sharing system which gives efficient tool that interchange ideas by sharing notes is one way to support and help improve the learning process in terms of education in this global pandemic crisis; second, the Dashboard and Events features were applied that serves as a user-friendly web-based social notes platform and allows users to identify and organize their notes which would increase student learning experience and improve teacher teaching approach; and third, the software evaluation is conducted by using ISO 9216 as a survey tool for evaluating the systems efficiency, portability, reliability, functionality, usability, and maintainability which is required for the systems set for uses, performance, and function.

The project shows that it serves a social notes sharing system that assists in sharing information with users; thus, the development of a social notes sharing system under the new normal educational approach should do for plans of the system is to add voice recording and hand gesture recognition to help users with disabilities; second, add authentication to verify the identity of the user; and third, add a text input scanner.

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